

Exploring the Boundaries of Non-State Units: Using Qualitative Techniques for Spatial Analysis

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Scholars that are interested in accounting for space in their research may run into difficulty when studying phenomena at a sub-state unit of analysis. Recent literature argues that theory and causal mechanisms should motivate the incorporation of crucial components of spatial analysis such as the selection of units of analysis (Darmofal 2015; Harbers and Ingram 2018; Soifer 2019) and the construction of spatial weights (Neumayer and Plümper 2016). This can be a challenge for studies that use jurisdictional units, such as provinces, districts, or other government administration units (Soifer 2019, 96). Additionally, this can be particularly difficult for studies that utilize non-jurisdictional units that have some cohesive ethnic, religious, or power grouping, such as Kurdistan, the Uighur region of China, or gang-controlled territories. This, however, may not just be an issue for informal, occupied, or sub-states, but also those with fluid boundaries. In addition to ethnic or religious groupings, this can be applied to the study of areas controlled by gangs, insurgent territorial control, immigration patterns, or the spread of pandemics, among other topics. These examples elucidate difficulties in selecting the appropriate unit of analysis, especially as people's perceptions of unit boundaries may be different than that of researchers (Soifer 2019, 104). For non-jurisdictional units it may be particularly difficult to find sufficient available shapefiles and geo-referenced data, which may not exactly line up with the units needed to study outcomes of interest. It is valid to use available data to study subjects that do not follow traditional political boundaries, or phenomena with non-jurisdictional units (Soifer 2019, 108). However, it is important to think critically about how to choose the units of analysis that best align with the outcome under study. In the example provided later (see section "The Hypothetical"), we work through the different ways in which a study to understand civilian support for the Islamic State could be navigated using our approach.

The Problem

A core issue in spatial analysis is the consideration of "place" and ensuring that the units of analysis we use capture the underlying processes that we study. The selection of the correct unit is important for ameliorating the modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP), "which makes it very likely that findings will change as they are measured across differently drawn spatial units, whether different in scale, or different in shape, that is, where the borders are drawn" (Soifer 2019, 93). The best solution for dealing with this issue is to select a unit that corresponds with our theory (Darmofal 2015; Harbers and Ingram 2018; Soifer 2019). However, as Soifer (2019, 104-5) notes, the appropriate units may be obvious in some cases but ambiguous in others. Furthermore, data disaggregated to the appropriate unit is difficult to find in some cases, especially for phenomena that do not follow political boundaries. Social scientists may therefore have to compromise accuracy for availability. Below, we offer two examples that highlight the difficulties of using non-jurisdictional units at the sub-national and transnational levels.

In a separate project, we study variation in ethnic group mobilization in the Philippines. We collected event-level data by coding news sources via NexisUni and are only able to filter this within provinces, a jurisdictional unit of analysis. While it would be ideal to use groups as the unit of analysis, they span across provinces and do not align with the boundaries of the provincial units. A potential solution to this issue might have been to use neighborhood- or city-level jurisdictional units, but there were data availability problems. For instance, we could not accurately geo-tag our data for cities because the information was not reported in the news sources. In these cases, we could only geo-tag our data at an aggregated level (city or province).

Studies which include the Kurdish nation also illustrate the difficulty in studying outcomes that do not align with traditional political boundaries. In this instance, the “boundaries” of Kurdistan cut across not only the state boundaries of Syria, Iraq, Turkey, and Iran but also provincial boundaries within these states. For example, in a previous attempt to study Kurdistan, we compiled a shapefile using provincial-level data (see Figures 1 and 2) using several sources (Kurdish Institute, n.d.; The Kurdish Project, n.d.; Izady 2015). By merging selected parts of Syria, Turkey, Iran, and Iraq deemed to be Kurdish-majority areas (see Figure 2), we can roughly distinguish the shape of what should be Kurdistan. The provincial map at the bottom of Figure 1 is likely inclusive of portions of provinces that are not considered to be part of Kurdistan by Kurdish peoples or scholars. For example, only part of Aleppo province is regarded as part of Kurdistan: the city of Aleppo, for instance, is not included. Alternatively, it may not include what should be considered as part of Kurdistan. Therefore, using either aggregated jurisdictional units at the state level or units disaggregated to the provincial level may misrepresent the spatial relationship of interest as they do not align with the “boundaries” of Kurdistan.

Figure 1. Map of Kurdistan A.rea

Approximation of Kurdish-majority area using Google Maps in April 2018. Area selected based on the following sources: Kurdish Institute, n.d.; The Kurdish Project, n.d.; Izady, 2015; Izady 2018.¹

Studies of Kurdistan may benefit from using city- or neighborhood-level units of analysis, yet there was no source readily available to help us identify the boundaries. One potential solution is to collect data on the boundaries and to build an original shapefile, but this process may be expensive and time consuming (Soifer 2019, 108). However, even this process may not yield an accurate understanding of the boundaries of an area like Kurdistan as the boundaries are contested. In this case,

varying groups may have different understandings of delineations between “Kurdish” areas and “Syrian” areas; an Iraqi from Dohuk may understand differently where Kurdistan starts and ends than a Kurd from a different city. Given the potential issues with studying non-jurisdictional units outlined in the previous section— notably, the difficulty in finding shapefiles and available data—we offer some ways to approach researching such units in the next section.

Figure 2. Merged Shapefile of Kurdistan

Kurdish-majority provinces selected based on the following sources: Kurdish Institute, n.d.; The Kurdish Project, n.d.; Izady, 2015; Izady, 2018.

The Solution

As previously discussed, trying to analyze and discern the boundaries of non-jurisdictional units, such as groups of people, areas affected by natural disasters, or the spread of disease, can be challenging. We offer a few potential solutions to resolve this issue.

The first potential solution is to travel to the region of interest and conduct interviews, focus groups, or surveys to ascertain the demarcations of such units. Researchers could use tablets or similar electronic devices and ask respondents to draw their understanding of the boundaries. The boundaries of the units of interest could then be created by aggregating and averaging the drawings of each respondent. A shapefile could then be created by sub-setting countries’ shapefiles in programs such as R at a lower level of aggregation. For example, in the case of Kurdistan, one would merge relevant municipal units in the shapefiles of Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Turkey. One could also use programs such as ArcGIS or QGIS and create a shapefile by uploading an image of the aggregated boundary. This approach

1. The Izady (2018) map highlights some Kurdish-majority areas in more inland Turkey and near the Turkmenistan border; our conceptualization is a conservative depiction because those were not areas that the other sources highlighted.

is the reverse of the traditional large-N/quantitative to small-n/qualitative case study mixed-method research design prescribed by Lieberman (2005) and Seawright and Gerring (2008). The approach outlined below may provide clues about boundaries, causal processes, spatial weights, and other aspects of the outcome of interest to ensure measurement validity.

However, an important caveat to delineating boundaries using qualitative data collection is that, as with many subjects in the social sciences, such boundaries are socially or culturally constructed to a certain extent, therefore the conception of the phenomena's frontier may vary from person to person. An individual living in the space outside the non-jurisdictional area may have a different conception of where the boundary lies than someone living within it. Furthermore, the units of analysis may not be homogenous and contestation over their boundaries may occur among those living within the area. For example, Kurds, Arabs (of various ethnicities), Persians, Azeris, Turks, Lurs, and Syrians all live in the area known as Kurdistan. However, each group may give different answers to questions about Kurdistan's boundaries at the neighborhood, city, or state level. Thus, even these qualitative techniques may yield contested boundaries which may create replicability issues (Soifer 2019, 99).

To alleviate some of these issues, we recommend interviewing people in different roles and varying relationships to the outcome of interest to the extent possible for triangulation purposes. Examples of different groups of interviewees may include members of the ethnic group of interest, members of different ethnic groups in the area, as well as local politicians, scholars, development aid workers, health officials, law enforcement, store owners, and teachers, among others. As part of interviews, subjects could be asked to demarcate on a map the neighborhoods or cities they recognize as Kurdish or non-Kurdish dominant; or respondents could be asked to fill in pre-drawn geographical units of neighborhoods. An alternate approach would be to overlay a grid on a city or state map and have respondents shade in their understanding of the Kurdish-dominant areas. Those who are not familiar with Kurdish neighborhoods or areas could be asked to mark areas they are familiar with, and the groups that are dominant there. Researchers could use information about where other groups are dominant to inform their understanding of Kurdish-dominant areas. As previously mentioned, a researcher could create a shapefile of the region of interest based on an aggregation of respondents' drawings of the boundaries. One could also create several shapefiles based on the results from different groups of interviewees if the

results are significantly different, which may be an important finding on its own.

Traveling to the region of interest and conducting fieldwork to identify boundaries may not be possible for a variety of reasons. Consequently, we offer several options to gather this information remotely. First, interviews conducted remotely through Skype or other videoconferencing software could be used to collect information about boundaries. Related files, for the drawing of maps as discussed above, could be easily shared, filled in, and sent back electronically. Another option would be to work with local survey agencies or academics, who could liaise with the local community, ask questions, and bring tablets for drawing maps. Local partners are more proximate to the phenomena and could leverage their social networks to contact law enforcement, politicians, or aid workers and ask them questions about ethnic-majority areas and to draw the boundaries on a tablet. Proxies could also email interviewees a survey or questionnaire and blank template for the boundaries to be drawn, scanned, and sent back to the researcher. A third solution is to apply the same techniques to diasporic members, refugees, former gang members, former insurgents, and others. The researcher could still ask interview subjects to draw the borders of the unit of interest on a tablet or similar device. Similarly, scholars could work with local social service providers and non-profits in refugee camps to schedule interviews. These organizations may have resources to set up a room for a videoconference interview (e.g., Zoom or Skype). Finally, researchers can use crowd-sourcing programs such as Zooniverse and ask respondents to identify the boundaries of a region of interest. Researchers may want to use more than one method for the purposes of triangulation.

In addition to getting enough information about non-jurisdictional units to construct a shapefile, qualitative methods can provide insight into the appropriate spatial weight matrices, the patterns of the interaction between the spatial units, for analysis. As Harbers and Ingram (2017) note, the selection of an appropriate spatial weight matrix (W) is important because it underlies assumptions about the regression and the results. The W demarcates the relationship between the units. Interviews with individuals who live near the non-jurisdictional area or members of proximate groups may reveal how the spatial units interact in practice. For example, are refugee populations typically relocated into one unit from another and if so, what is the trajectory? The W might also be useful to account for the informal historical and cultural institutions and their influence on the present context. For example, many Kurdish subgroups did and continue to operate with tribal kin groups for political

organization, governance, among other societal activities (McDowall 2000). Kurds within a specific area may relate to our outcome of interest differently based on historical and cultural contexts, which a spatial weight could capture. This qualitative technique comports with Neumayer and Plümper's (2016) recommendation to select the *W* based on causal processes and theory. We add that there may not be a theoretical reason for a consistent *W* across the entire shapefile; depending on the information gained through interviews, the researcher may opt to construct a hybrid *W* where there is variation in the spatial relationships between units. Furthermore, one may want to run more than one regression based on different *W* if interviews reveal that the relationship between the spatial units varied over time. For example, were refugee populations relocated to one area at one time and then to another area at a different time? If so, the relationships between the variables of interest may have changed.

The Hypothetical

In this section, we outline a proposed process for collecting data on a project about civilian support for the Islamic State in Syria. This subject would be best studied at a disaggregated level—such as a neighborhood or family level. Given the ongoing Syrian conflict and diminishing state capacity, the potential for data availability for the neighborhood level is low and data at the family level is not available. For this project, it would be important to understand which part of the country falls into the area known as Kurdistan. Historic Kurdish areas will likely have different trends given Kurdish militants' fight against the Islamic State (Jayamaha 2014; Salih 2015; Jones et al. 2017). Conceptualizing what constitutes Syria is significant for understanding where Syrian Kurdistan is, but also in finding an appropriate unit of analysis and how Kurdistan should be differentiated from the rest of Syria. The appeal of the following approach is centered on providing researchers a process by which to solicit and quantify inductive measures in the early stages of analysis.

Given the difficulties of traveling to Syria for research, we would leverage virtual tools to determine a scope of analysis. Through this method, we could engage with multiple groups, including academics, politicians, and journalists currently or recently in the field, as well as subject matter experts and recently repatriated Syrian refugees. Researchers could solicit different groups based on their needs and timelines, while considering IRB approval and other necessary measures. Researchers may select different groups based on their own constraints. For example, IRB approval is easier for working with

elite subjects (i.e., politicians) as opposed to vulnerable populations (i.e., refugees).

After identifying the appropriate groups for outreach, we would select a suite of Syrian maps at various levels to provide subjects for denoting Kurdish-, Islamic State-, and other majority areas. As we are concerned with Syria writ large, we select a country-level map for an overall image appended with province-level maps with topography, highways, and other broad indicators for subjects' reference. It is up to the researchers' discretion about how to disseminate and receive the maps. For instance, these maps could be hosted on a platform, such as Zooniverse, that allows users to draw and submit online. Alternatively, maps could be attached to an email, downloaded by subjects, drawn in stock applications (e.g., Microsoft Paint), and sent back. Subjects could also print the maps, physically draw on them, and then scan and send them back electronically. In addition to the maps, we would include a short survey for the respondents, including the last time of travel to have a point of reference, which can be informative once the files are digitized. Researchers' choice of how to disseminate their maps depends partially on their target populations and considerations of respondents' anonymity. Once the submissions are collected, the input needs to be standardized. Physical maps should be scanned and converted into images. In ArcGIS or QGIS, the images could be converted into shapefiles. The final shapefile could be created by averaging the boundaries created from respondents' maps. Additionally, depending on research needs, shapefiles could be created for different time periods.

Once a shapefile—or series of shapefiles—is constructed, researchers can determine the most effective means of collecting data. Ideally, we would again enact a similar approach to collect data, whether by retracing our process with interviewees for determining the units of analysis. If available data is georeferenced, it could be sorted into the units of analysis that were constructed—using the previous approach—for the study. Other ways to collect data could include sampling or restructuring of available data. For instance, if the units of interest are disparate, researchers may opt for sampling households as opposed to collecting data at the district level. Alternatively, if data is collected at the district or province level, it could be sliced into different units of analysis, informed by the aforementioned process. With this approach, researchers could add the indicators for majority areas, in efforts to capture variation attributed to immeasurable sociopolitical institutions and therefore provide some alleviation of omitted variable bias.

Conclusion

It is increasingly important to study non-jurisdictional phenomena as the world becomes more connected and population flows become easier and more frequent. Accordingly, many contemporary social science and policy issues involve units of analysis that do not comport with traditional political boundaries, such as terrorist group cells, insurgent safe havens, refugee populations, or diasporas. Thus, it is imperative to find adaptable, feasible means to acquire and study these outcomes, and it is the responsibility of social scientists to find spatial units appropriate to studying their outcome variable. We recommend a qualitative to quantitative approach to ameliorate this problem: by using qualitative interviews of individuals familiar with the non-jurisdictional region, researchers can more accurately create a shapefile and select the proper spatial

weight matrix to properly measure their outcome of interest. If the solutions provided in this article are not feasible, Soifer (2019) recommends other approaches, such as shifting the study to a more aggregated level or stipulating data availability as criteria for choosing the level of analysis (109). Each of the strategies outlined here come with tradeoffs. When seeking to collect more fine-grained data, there are obvious costs associated for researchers and in-country data collection. However, such an approach could lead to greater accuracy. In contrast, data at a more aggregated level may be readily accessible but lead to potential misspecification of the outcome of interest. Alternatively, the latter may mean that the researcher will not be able to study their research question and hypotheses of choice, but instead need to tailor it to the data available.

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